

УДК:159.923: 811.111

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SCIENTIFIC APPROACHES TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF LANGUAGE COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TRAINING

The basic approaches to the development of language competence of students in the conditions of studying a foreign language, as well as the peculiarities of thinking activities in the speech process, have been analysed and generalized. The psychological essence of educational activity of students aimed at mastering a foreign language has been considered. It was clarified that none of the approaches takes into account the specifics of real mental actions that a person performs in the process of generation and perception of speech statement. Such actions represent an essential basis for language competence, and their purposeful formation is an effective way of optimizing student learning in higher education environment.

Key words: language competence, speech perception, speech production, mental actions formation, foreign language speech.

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НАУКОВІ ПІДХОДИ ДО РОЗВИТКУ МОВНОЇ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТІ СТУДЕНТІВ У ПРОЦЕСІ НАВЧАННЯ ІНОЗЕМНІЙ МОВИ

Проаналізовано й узагальнено основні підходи до розвитку мовної компетентності студентів в умовах вивчення іноземної мови, а також особливості розумових дій у процесі мовлення. Розглянута психологічна сутність навчальної діяльності студентів, націлена на опанування іноземної мови. Аналіз існуючих підходів до розвитку мовної компетентності студентів показав сутнісні відмінності в розумінні змісту і структури пізнавальних і практичних дій, спрямованих на освоєння іноземної мови. Було виявлено що усі підходи об'єднує те, що ні в одному з них не враховується специфіка реальних розумових дій, які здійснює людина в процесі породження і сприйняття мовленнєвого висловлювання. Такі дії являють собою сутнісну основу мовної компетентності, та їх цілеспрямоване формування - ефективний шлях оптимізації навчання студентів в умовах навчання у ВНЗ.

Ключові слова: мовна компетентність, сприйняття мовленнєвого висловлювання, породження мовленнєвого висловлювання, формування розумових дій, іншомовне мовленнєве висловлювання.

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НАУЧНЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ К РАЗВИТИЮ ЯЗЫКОВОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Проведен анализ и обобщение основных подходов к развитию языковой компетентности студентов в условиях изучения иностранного языка, а также особенностей мыслительных действий в процессе речи. Рассмотрена психологическая сущность учебной деятельности студентов, нацеленной на овладение иностранным языком. Анализ существующих подходов к развитию языковой компетентности студентов показал существенные различия в понимании содержания и структуры познавательных и практических действий, направленных на освоение иностранного языка. Было выявлено, что ни один из подходов не учитывает специфику реальных умственных действий, которые человек выполняет в процессе воспроизведения и восприятия речи. Такие действия представляют собой существенную основу языковой компетентности, и их целенаправленное формирование является эффективным способом оптимизации обучения студентов в высших учебных заведениях.

Ключевые слова: языковая компетентность, восприятие речевого высказывания, порождение речевого высказывания, формирования умственных действий, иноязычное речевое высказывание.

Introduction. The problem of language competence is quite acute in the context of modern processes of Euro-integration. Learning a foreign language becomes essential for almost every specialist, scientist, and student in the conditions of expanding the boundaries of the economic, educational and scientific space. At the same time, it is necessary that the available methods of teaching a foreign language meet the requirements of the trainees, show high efficiency, and give the expected result as much as possible. Nowadays there are several reasons why it is necessary to look for new ways to solve this problem. Firstly, the curriculum in universities is limited to a certain number of hours allocated for studying a foreign language. Of course, this number of hours is not enough to learn a foreign language at an appropriate level. Secondly, traditional methods of teaching (theoretical and communicative approach) do not give high results. Thirdly, when choosing methods and means of teaching, basic principles of the functioning of human memory and thinking are not taken into consideration. Because of this, we have an inefficient formal approach to the teaching of a foreign language and as a result the knowledge of students, that can not provide the work of a psychological mechanism of perception and the generation of a foreign speech statement.

It is necessary to identify and systematically study the conditions for the optimal application of psychological mechanisms in the context of the content and structure of learning activities within the framework of university learning. The task is to trace precisely which approaches in the teaching of a foreign lan-

guage based on psychological regularities, are relied on the inseparable link between language, speech and thinking.

In addition to that, it is important to disclose the psychological essence of students' learning activities aimed at mastering a foreign language through the analysis of theoretical and empirical approaches. A number of complex psychological mechanisms provides the implementation of speech activity at all phases (levels) of its realization. These mechanisms have been and still are the subject of research by many psychologists and psycholinguists. Our task is to identify those approaches that can ensure an effective optimization of the learning process of a foreign language in the conditions of higher education.

The **aim** of our study is to determine the correspondence of existing teaching methods to the goals of developing the students' language competence in mastering a foreign language in the conditions of university education.

Discussion. Language competence and speech activity are meaningfully and functionally different elements of the internal substructure of speech experience, having independent functions in the process of verbal development of the personality of the world. This kind of competence forms and formalizes language and speech knowledge into a single system, and with the help of speech activity, the formation and formulation of thought takes place, which in general leads to the conceptualization of the world [1]. The concept of language competence includes the ability of a student to perceive and produce meaningful statements, to know and use the transformational rules of the language. Analyzing the existing methods in the teaching of a foreign language, one can distinguish the following approaches: 1) cognitive; 2) communicative; 3) intensive training; 4) e-learning.

The cognitive approach is learning based on the assimilation of theoretical rules, which are involuntarily transformed into practical actions when performing exercises. The teacher concentrates on the theory and the application of grammatical rules beyond the real practice of communication. Students learn the rules of grammar, but do not introduce knowledge into practice. Many students have a barrier in the transition to free speech, which means that the mechanism of the speech generation is not developed.

The communicative approach, on the contrary, intensively develops the process of speaking, immersing trainees in communicative situations. But at the same time the students do not have a basic idea of the holistic system of the studied language, distinguishing grammatical constructions in the speech flow with great difficulty. As a result, students can speak but do not feel mistakes because they have the mechanical knowledge gained through memorization of speech clichés and active vocabulary without relying on basic knowledge of the system of language and its regularities.

Intensive training resorts to the use of mnemonic techniques. They are based on frequent repetition and it is assumed that the frequent repetition of phrases and words can lead to the involuntary mastery of the language without understanding its rules and regularities. An example is the intensive methods of studying the foreign language of Kitaigorodskaya G.A. [2]. This method emphasizes the importance of collective activity in teaching, the use of opportunities that are included in the team within the interaction of individuals, the interaction of the collective and the individual, in the patterns of the impact of collective activity on the success of an individual. The method of activating of Kitaygorodskaya G.A. includes the following basic methodological conditions that ensure the effectiveness of the learning process: 1) various forms of collective interaction; 2) person-oriented communication; 3) role organization of the educational process; 4) concentration in the organization of educational material and educational process; 5) multifunctionality of exercises (involves simultaneous and parallel mastery of language material and speech activity). In these principles, the method of activation most clearly and fully reflects the concept of intensive learning foreign languages.

In addition to intensive training, there are a number of techniques based on involuntary mechanical memorization at the level of intervention in the subconscious of the trainee (suggestopedia, 25th frame). Suggestopedia is pedagogical science with the use of peripheral perceptions. That is everything that does not fall into the conscious focus, but perceived by peripheral vision, tactile sensations, sound, smells, colour, etc. This information is perceived by the brain and stored in the subconscious. Georgy Lozanov, the creator of the science of pedagogy and its pedagogical application, believes that the hidden potential of the brain of the students is mobilized in the new organization of communication training. However, within impressive results it turned out that knowledge obtained mechanically does not transfer to the new situations and is not capable of the development. Moreover, there is a real danger of negative influence on human health. An example of this is the groups of the first Lozanov's subjects [3].

The 25th frame technique is also effective for learning, memorizing, suggesting ideas. This technique involves the effect of a certain hidden image inserted into the video frame between the frames, the student's consciousness and subconsciousness. But the effect of the 25th frame on the human psychics has not been studied finally and is considered rather risky.

One of the modern approaches is e-learning. This method is intended to optimize the process of mastering the language through the use of technical facilities. However, on the example of the Lingualeo training program, one can see that the process is organized on the basis of the technical principles of the

organization of training, does not reflect the essence of the language as a whole. Undoubtedly, the material is presented in a gaming form with a bright interface; it includes a lot of audio, video and text materials, but taking into consideration all this variety there is no systematic representation of grammar. The actions of the trainee are directed to mechanical memorization rather than entering into the structure of semantic interrelations in the sentence.

All these approaches are come together considering the fact that none of them takes into account the specifics of the real mental actions that a person performs in the process of generating and perception of speech.

In contrast to the described approaches, the competence approach in teaching a foreign language has included a psychological component in this process. The most complete description of the psychological mechanisms of speech activity is presented in studies within the tradition of the native school of psycholinguistics (the school of Artemov V.A. – Zhinkin N.I. – Zimnyaya I.A.). In the works of Zhinkin N.I. and Zimnyaya I.A. it is presented a holistic scientific concept of psychological mechanisms of speech activity. According to this concept, the main psychological mechanisms of speech activity are: the mechanism of comprehension, the mnemonic organization of speech activity (first of all, the mechanism of speech memory), as well as the mechanism of predictive analysis and speech synthesis (the mechanism of speech prediction or, what is the same as speech prediction) [4; 5].

Of course, the most important mechanism of speech activity is the mechanism of comprehension. This mechanism provides a mental analysis of both the content of the speech (in the first place), its structural organization, and linguistic formalization. The mechanism of comprehension through the analytic and synthetic activity of the cerebral cortex of the cerebral hemispheres is realized on the basis of the use of all basic mental actions and operations (comparison, correlation, generalization, classification, analysis and synthesis).

However, these studies with all their scientific depth give little to the practitioner's methodology. An exception is the works by T.V. Sergeyeva [6; 7] devoted to the involuntary memorization of language material based on the principles of developing learning [8 – 10]. The background of the course was based on the linguistic concept of the internal communication of the message with a definite meaningful grammatical form of its expression in the language. A special form of expression of this correlation in the English language is a strictly fixed place of words in the structure of the English sentence and the morpheme, the change of which correlates with the change in the meaning of the statement. The highlighting of these links is carried out through linguistic knowledge specific actions on syntagmatic and paradigmatic language analysis.

The effectiveness of such memorization depends on the breadth of meaningful and content orientation in the educational material, which is required

prior to the implementation of the appropriate system of cognitive actions. Such an orientation creates an installation to hold the results of actions as necessary conditions for the achievement of the ultimate goal and thereby determines the actual mnemonic effect. The optimal conditions for the high efficiency of material remembering are provided if the content of the general orienting semantic problem is to identify the essence of the subject. This allows maximizing systemacy and awareness of actions. Such a task ensures the continuous operation of memory in the process of mastering the entire object and creates optimal conditions for this work. In the process of deducing the essence of an object, the development of the semantic level of students' activity occurs, which creates an installation to hold the results of the actions of the students as necessary conditions for the achievement of the ultimate goal, throughout the work with the subject, that is, provides the work of memory. Students' awareness of the essence of an object creates an opportunity for them to build their own actions independently and, consequently to understand the system of actions. From the point of view of rational use of memory, learning is most effective at the unintentionally memorizing of knowledge in the very process of their learning.

Conclusions. The analysis of existing approaches to the development of language competence of students showed essential differences in understanding the content and structure of cognitive and practical actions aimed at the mastering of a foreign language. The generalization has distinguished four main-streams: 1) a cognitive approach, where it is assumed that theoretical rules are involuntarily transformed into practical actions in the process of performing exercises; 2) a communicative approach where it is assumed that simulation of situations of real communication leads to the development of speech skills without theoretical generalizations; 3) intensive training where it is assumed that mnemonic techniques based on frequent repetition can lead to the involuntary mastering of a language without understanding its regularities; 4) e-learning, where it is assumed that the statistical approach optimizes the mastering of the language, and the methods are subject to technical facilities. All these approaches are come together considering the fact that none of them takes into account the specifics of the real mental actions that a person performs in the process of generating and perception of speech. Such actions are an essential basis of language competence, and their purposeful formation is an effective way of optimizing students' education in the conditions of university education.

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Надійшла до редколегії 21.01.2018 р.